

Local Government in Australia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Australia: An Introduction

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There are increasing efforts across local government in Australia to directly involve residents in local decision-making. This could be undertaken through a range of consultative and deliberative processes, particularly with regard to determining budget allocations, service levels and long-term community strategic planning. In many cases consultation is required under legislation and a recent survey of councils in Victoria and New South Wales revealed that, for many, consultation was still seen as primarily a compliance activity. However, practice is gradually changing and more councils are building the capacity to conduct meaningful engagement with their communities on a range of issues.

For example, community satisfaction surveys have become a common tool to ascertain what residents expect in terms of service delivery and performance. These surveys vary in their implementation but in general they target service users through feedback surveys. In addition, councils may carry other activities to canvas the community's thoughts, such as setting up stalls in shopping centres or engaging external agencies to carry out wider resident surveys. This has helped local governments to identify gaps between expectations and performance and by highlighting where performance improvement is needed. Increasingly, the findings of these surveys form the basis of local government annual reports and are being fed into the major whole-of-organisation service delivery review processes. These reviews, in varying forms, are generally required by the various Acts which govern local government across Australia.

Other engagement mechanisms are also increasingly used including focus groups and deliberative tools such as citizen's juries. For example, from August to November 2019, the City of Sydney in NSW convened a citizens jury of 50 members of the community. The jury considered, and made recommendations on, concepts that should be introduced by 2050 in order to facilitate the realisation of the communities' vision for the city. This included strategic objectives such as the improved involvement and representation of the First Peoples of Australia in community decision-making.

For many small councils, capability and resource limitations are impacting on their ability to actively engage their communities and further innovation is required.

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